

READERS' PERCEPTION OF NEWSPAPER COVERAGE OF WOMEN IN POLITICS IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract

This study analyzed the readers' perception of newspaper coverage of women in politics, evaluating the views of Enugu state residents. The success or failure of any nation lies in the hands of the media. Against this postulation, this study evaluates the level of success by the print media (newspaper) in promoting democratic ideals by providing prompt, reliable and useful information to the masses and policy makers. This study also rates the newspaper as a print media's zeal to work for the political development and democratic security of the country's electoral system through effective media coverage of women in politics. This seminar is anchored on analysing Enugu state residents' views on how the newspapers in Nigeria report news and issues about women in politics. This study has as specific objective of finding out the peoples' perception on newspaper coverage of women in politics in Enugu State. The survey method design was adopted for this study. From a projected population estimate of 4,411,100, a sample size of 384 was drawn using the Australian sample size calculator with confidence level of 95% and confidence interval of 5.0%. Instrument for data collection was questionnaire. The findings revealed that women mostly feature in stories about domestic violence, accidents, and natural disasters than stories about their professional abilities and expertise most especially political affairs. Respondents in Enugu state perceived newspapers coverage of women in politics as inadequate. From the findings the researcher recommended that the print media most especially the newspapers should report stories that pertains to women in politics given it an in depth coverage to encourage more women to become interested in politics. Then, future researchers should investigate how the social media report women in politics as the traditional media are not reporting it adequately.

Keywords: Women, Politics, Perception, Newspapers, and Coverage

Introduction

Women have been in the government and different institutions, and the women occupy critical segment of the population everywhere in the globe. This historical tendency is well known fact that is not debatable, although women are increasingly being elected to be heads of state and government. In the post-colonial era, the women's struggle dated back to the 19th century when the like of Amina of Zaria, Madam Tinubu of Lagos, Olufuami Layo Ransom Kuti, Margaret Ekpo and so on fought for the people's rights. In the recent past, some women made land marks in politics in Nigeria where they continue to prove their mettle, the likes of Ngozi Okonjo Iweala, Uche Ekwunife, Pauline Tallen, Oby Ezekwesili, Abike Dabiri Erewa, Ezeilo Cecilia, and others. As of October 2019, the global participation rate of women in national-level parliaments was 24.5%. In 2013, women accounted for 8% of all national leaders and 2% of all presidential posts. Furthermore, 75% of all female prime ministers and presidents have taken office in the past two decades. Women face a number of challenges that affect their ability to participate in political life and become political leaders. Several countries are exploring measures that may increase women's participation in government at all levels, from the local to the national and international.

However, more women are pursuing leadership positions in the present day. The issues pertaining to women holding pivotal positions of power have drawn global attention. In spite clamours for improvement in women participation in public life across the world, Nigeria appears to be moving in

the gradual positive direction. Women have remained a vastly underrepresented minority in the halls of political power throughout Nigerian history. Since the resumption of electoral democracy in 1999, public campaigns, proposed legislative reforms and internal measures within political parties have attempted to address the gaping gender imbalance. Yet assessments of the performance of female candidates in Nigeria's most recent general elections revealed a disturbing trend: women's representation in elected and appointed office has not only failed to increase positively but appears to be in decline. As part of its wider interest in understanding the nature of electoral democracy and citizen participation in Nigeria, the Centre for Democracy and Development (CDD) commissioned a series of studies on women's participation following Nigeria's 2019 elections. The first of these, entitled "How Women Fared in the 2019 Elections", considered the scale and performance of women candidates in the last general elections. Experiences have revealed that women folk do not have equal status with men folk in elective posts in political circles which negates goal three of MDGs (now SDGs) which is gender equality. Active participation of women in politics cannot be achieved without genuine communication system. Communication serve as a vehicle through which different segments of people relate with each other. Communication system is an approach to issues, in respective of their personality. Effective communication of political dispensation can only be achieved through mass media. The mass media have the potential to assist in the constant promotion of women participation in politics by planning and mounting messages such as sustainable enlightenment campaigns for general awareness about the potential leadership qualities of women and their role in sustainable development in Nigeria. Enebek, (2008). The Nairobi world conference to review and appraise the achievements of the UN Decade for women in 1985 and the Beijing fourth world conference for women in 1995, both had top on the agenda issue concerning women and the media. This conference brought about the importance of the media in the quest for gender equity in development, despite their international conferences and policies aimed at gender friendliness. However women's participation in Nigerian politics is undermined by the way the media politics are reported as an exclusively male domain. Nwankwo (1996 p. 11). Nwankwo asserted that one important factor in the pursuit of gender equality in politics is the media. The researcher aimed here to critically analyze the readers' perception of newspaper coverage of women in politics, evaluating the views of Enugu state residents

Statement of the Problem

Some of the key responsibilities of the mass media in every society include keeping surveillance of the environment, responding to the environmental factors, entertaining the public, correlating various parts of the society, being a watchdog to political activities, keeping society updated with sports news, etc. However, the role of the mass media in general and newspaper in particular in providing information to the society cannot be over emphasized. According to Nwankwo (1996): The Nairobi world conference to review and appraise the achievements of the UN Decade for women in 1985 and the Beijing fourth world conference for women in 1995, both had top on the agenda issue concerning women and the media. This conference brought about the importance of the media in the quest for gender equity in development, despite their international conferences and policies aimed at gender friendliness. However, women's participation in Nigerian politics is undermined by the way the media politics are reported as an exclusively male domain. Nwankwo (1996 p. 11). Nwankwo asserted that one important factor in the pursuit of gender equality in politics is the media. It is instructive that accusing fingers were pointed at the media for their perceived role in previous elections in the country. The media were perceived to have failed in their role to adequately inform and educate the electorates while maintaining neutrality in treating issues including election results and the use of the media by political candidates. As a result, the electorates lost trust and confidence in the media with its attendant political apathy and violence. This is especially so with state owned media and some privately owned media that were found to be supportive of the ruling party. Even the media regulatory body, the National Broadcasting Commission Most studies on media and politics have focused on media coverage of the presidential election, governorship election, or influence of the media on the electoral process. It appears that none has been specifically conducted on readers' perception on newspapers as a print medium coverage of women participation in politics. In Enugu state, women have been involved in politics to the extent that Deputy governor of the recent past state leadership is

a woman, other women are in notable positions, but the pertinent question is were they not performing or that newspaper industry failed to report events relating to them. To this end, the researcher sought to analyze how people view the newspaper coverage of women participation in politics in Enugu state.

Objective of the Study

The general objective of this study anchored on analyzing readers' perception on newspaper coverage of women in politics in Enugu state. The specific objectives of the study are to;

1. Investigate how newspapers readers resident in Enugu State perceive newspaper coverage of women in politics
2. Find out if the newspapers gave enough prominence and depth to stories on women in politics.

Research Questions

The research questions raised from the objectives of the study are:

1. To what extent do the newspapers readers' residents in Enugu state perceive newspapers coverage of stories on women in politics?
2. How often do the newspapers give enough prominence and depth to stories relating to women in politics

Significance of the Study

The outcome of this seminar will immensely benefit not only to the women both those in politics and those that support them, but also print media organizations most especially newspaper houses, government, then entire society at large. This study will benefit the academia and equally give insight to researchers that will like to do more study on this topic or related ones

Limitations of the Study

The limitations of this study are basically the lack of materials, and time. The available published materials on the print media coverage of women in politics are hard to reach due to scarcity of news print. The unwilling attitude of some persons to respond issue newspaper reportage of women in politics posed as limitation to the study.

However, some respondent complained of time stating that they busy with their works due hardship in the land, they cannot spare anytime to respond to issues that pertains to women in politics. The time allowed for this study was also a limitation. The time given for the completion of this study did not allow for the expansion of the scope.

Literature Review

Newspaper, as well as other print media like magazine, books, journals – are powerful and influential means of information gathering and dissemination. They cover different human activities and report such coverage to a host of their audience members through a process known as circulation. Different human angle stories are used for education, entertainment, mobilization, socialization and other functions of the audience of newspaper. Like other forms of mass media, people can get all sort of information they need from newspaper. The medium image held by the receiver causes expectations of the media content and may thus be assumed to have an influence on the receiver's choice of content as well as on his way of experiencing it and responding to it, McQuail and Windahl (1981, p.36). In line with the above information from the two mass communication experts, it could be said that through the publication of the newspapers, their readers can easily understand the prominence given to the issues relating to women in politics in Enugu state, Nigeria.

According to Maxwell (2016), the Concept of Perception as in the Webster revised unabridged dictionary extensively defined perception as (a) To obtain knowledge of through the senses; to receive impressions from by means of bodily organs; to take cognizance of the existence, character, or

identity of; by means of the senses; to see, hear, or feel; as, to perceive a distant ship; to perceive a discord. (b) To take intellectual cognizance of; to apprehend by the mind; to be convinced of by direct intuition; to note; to remark; to discern; to see; to understand. According to Feldman (1999: 10), "Perception is the sorting out, interpretation, analysis and integration of stimuli involving our sense organs and brain." Perception is conceived and often regarded as communication. This is because people often make evaluative judgements of what is desirable and undesirable in a community based on what they feel, experience, see, read, hear or talk about. Citizen's beliefs and values are therefore shaped by their perception of their world. People's thinking and beliefs also go a long way in determining their attitudes and opinions about individuals, motives, issues, events and society at large. In this regard, the mass media have been very influential agents in providing members of the society with the vital information upon which they can rationalise or critic issues and arrive at certain conclusions. When newspaper readers buy newspapers, they do so because they depend on it to know of current issues and what public opinion is regarding an issue of public significance. The media can be very helpful in examining the extent and ways in which newspaper readers affirm or disagree about corruption. Supporting the above position, McDonald, Hession, Rickard, et al (2002) while examining perception about government actions and policies, found that such perceptions were largely media influenced. However, it is pertinent to point out that how people perceive an issue is dependent upon certain fundamental factors. According to Severin, (2001) different psychological factors influence perceptions and they include past experience, cultural expectations, motivations, moods, needs and attitudes. This simply means that certain variations exist in perceptions and behaviours of different human beings.

Also, the types of issues covered, level of coverage given to politics and the overall media objectivity on the political activities in Nigeria can be determined through this newspaper coverage. According to the Agenda-setting theory of the press propounded by McCombs and Shaw (1972, 1976), audiences not only learn about public issues and other matters through the media, they also learn how much importance to attach to an issue or topic from the emphasis the mass media place upon it", so the level of media coverage given to the political activities by newspapers to understand its relevance in the country. To buttress this point made above (Hanson, 2005, p.383) asserts that: *The Agenda setting is a theory that holds that issues that are portrayed as important in the news media, become important to the public, that is the media set agenda for public debate.* As Agbese (1987, p.9) would state: *The press has power; it influences on every society democratic and autocratic are persuasive. For good or ill, the press, through medium (print or electronic) dictates public taste. It decides what the public should know and how and when it should know it, decides what is fit enough for public consumption.*

Women struggles date back to the 19TH century when women like Amina of Zaria, Madam Tinubu of Lagos, Olufunmilayo Ranson Kuti of Abeokuta, Margaret Ekpo and Hajiya Gabon Swabia among others fought to give women the pride of place in Nigeria's history. Even after the struggle for independence was over and Nigeria become an independent sovereign nation, women continued to contribute their quota in the post- independence march towards development and progress in the area of politics, the above named among others contributed immensely to the mobilization and sensitization of women with a view to ensuring that women are involved in the politics of the country. Andrew, H.C. (2015).

According to Hamid (2014), democracy cannot fully take its roots in societies or countries where there are not no free and vibrant mass media. Free and vibrant media actually free people's mind because they allow them the liberty to make contributions on how they are being governed or seen. Among other things, the media perform the functions of educating, informing and entertaining in addition to being a platform for mobilization; persuasion etc. vibrant media are interview with democratic governance because repressive regimes don't tolerate being put on the media scale of public discourse to examine their stewardship. Since the return to democratic rule in 1999, Nigerian women have tried to gained access to political decision making position by contesting for elective position at various levels. Their efforts however have not translated to appreciative gain as subsequent elections since 1999 revealed. Not only has there been marginal gain over the years which in itself is not very encouraging, but a decline in the number of elected female politicians in the 2015 general

election shows a manifestation of female political disempowerment, and this is more worrisome. Politics has strategic importance for women because the ultimate success of women's movement will rest heavily on effective use of the political process to get to political process. Women's ability to effectively use the political process to get to political positions may increase their representation in elective positions and effect public policies. However, it is very clear from Nigeria's experience that the political process is male dominated and men influence the process more than women (Lynn, 1978). Momodu (2003) submits that the issues of women's political participation and representation in politics and governance should be seen from four perspectives: Access, Participation, Representation and Transformation. Access to political institutions participations (which includes control of power within such institutions) quantitative and qualitative representation and the end result will be social and political transformation in the policy. Women's political empowerment can be enhanced when these four conditions are fulfilled. The view that women in politics matter is sustained by three reasons: First, politics is an important arena for decision making. Individuals who hold official position in government get to decide how to allocate scarce resource, such as tax revenues. Women in positions of authority and power can influence decision on issues that bother on women and impact positively on the lives of female gender (Paxton, 2007).

Globally, women constitute over half of the world's population and contribute in vital ways to societal development generally. In most societies, women assume some key roles, which are: mother, producer, and home-manager, and community organizer, socio-cultural and political activists. Of these many roles mentioned, the last has been engendered by women movement. In line with global trend, Nigerian women constitute nearly half of the population of the country. But despite the major roles they play with their population, women roles in the society are yet to be given recognition and the desired coverage by the newspapers.

However, Okunna and Omenugha (2012, p.76) posit that the great importance of newspaper as a mass medium derives from its role as a carrier of current information or news. Oparaugo (2021a) posits that through coverage of electioneering campaigns and airing of political advertisements, the media help in influencing voters' decision either in favor or against a given political party or candidate. (Hague & Harrop 2013, p.1). The negative connotation of politics, as seen in the phrase "play politics", for example, has been in use since at least 1853, when abolitionist Wendell Phillips declared: "We do not play politics; anti-slavery is no half-jest with us" (Satori, 2005, p.53).

Politics is the art or science concerned with winning election and holding control over a government, its arms or institution(s). Obasi (1999) argued that politics is "striving to share power or striving to influence the distribution of power, either among states or among groups within a state". The scholar went further to cite Lasswell (1958) to have defined politics as the science and art of who gets what, when and how?"

The above assertion is supported by Nnoli (1986) when he posited that politics is "all those activities which are directly or indirectly associated with the seizure of the state power, the consolidation of state power and the use of state power". Politics, according to Easton is "the authoritative allocation of values for a society." On the other hand, Umechukwu (2013) says the word "politics" in Nigerian context conjures up images of power domination and struggle to grab state apparatus. Politics therefore, exists in all human societies no matter how simple or primitive the society is. Akinfeleye (1995) states that, "Communication network required for making linkages possible is therefore to mind a powerful too for the sustenance of democracy." It is an accelerator of democracy a catalyst for effective democracy, tranquillizer for democracy and a lot of damage to democracy.

In Maxwell (2016, P.62), the global anti- corruption watchdog, the Transparency International (TI) affirms that by investigating and reporting on corruption, the media provides important counterpoint to the abuse of entrusted power for private gain, shedding light on the wrongdoings of public office holders and corporate executives alike. This obligatory function of the press has often met stiff resistance as those occupying top government positions deliberately become antagonistic to pressmen. This, in fact, has been the dilemma of the Nigerian journalist and the press generally since the dark

days of the military till date. The press is in the crucial business of checking the excesses of the powers that be and holding them accountable to the people for their stewardship. Supporting the above position Edeani (1993: 80) noted that: The Press is supposed to keep a watchful eye on what the government is doing and has the obligation on behalf of the public to criticize the government whenever it thinks that the government has not performed in the public interest, the press is thereby perpetually engaged in a running battle with the government. According to (Amadife, supra) Mass communication is a field and career of carrying out investigation, analysis, and reporting in the news media the true position of characters; events and situations for public awareness. He further contended that it is through mass communication that the public is exposed to the two sides of a coin in any matter of which one or both sides would have remained concealed. The central issue here is that: The media performs legitimate functions for society by providing correct information, knowledge and informed opinions about the issues of bad leadership style, poor political leadership and corruption and such contributions are helpful in adding value to the conduct of democratic politics. ...the press of the 1980's and 1990's had to squarely confront the scourge of internal colonialism at the hands of those who supposedly share kingship and racial, linguistic and cultural identity with those they so callously oppress. (Nwankwo, 1999: 223)

Empirical Review

In line with the topic of study, the researcher empirically reviewed studies from the area of media and politics. Ezinwa C. A. (2015) investigated how voters in Enugu State perceived the media coverage of the 2011 general elections in Nigeria. The study concentrated on registered voters in the south-eastern part of Nigeria. The Australian calculator was used to derive the sample size which stood at 405. Cluster sampling method was used to select respondents randomly to represent the population. The three hypotheses tested in the study using Chi-square formula received empirical support which showed that voters' exposure to electoral information in the media influenced their knowledge; their perception of the 2011 general election was influenced by their knowledge and their perception of media coverage of the 2011 general elections influenced their participation in the elections. The key findings of the study include that: radio remains a veritable means of reaching the electorates with information on electoral issues; the electorates have confidence in media reports; the electorates have high of knowledge of electoral issues; electorates' exposure to the media influenced their participation. It was recommended that radio should be used in disseminating information about election in Enugu State since voters have confidence in their reports.

Rasheed (2016) examined the role of broadcast media as an instrument of change during 2015 electioneering campaign in Nigeria. Broadcast Media played a key role in ensuring that Nigerians participate in the electoral process and that its outcomes are credible and acceptable to the generality of the entire nation. In an attempt to strengthen the effectiveness of broadcast media in promoting balanced, conflict sensitive reporting, a well-informed audience and accountability of public representatives and institutions, the broadcast media owners and editors shared information, advance mutual understanding, enhance cooperation, and harmonized their commitment on ethical issues relating to election reporting from their various organization. This paper employed quantitative research design, and the methodological approach is survey, the instrument of data collection is questionnaire with a sample size of 120 respondents and the sampling procedure is purposive sampling, and the method of data analysis is simple percentage and frequency tables. The paper achieved that broadcast media embarked on meaningful political awareness and public enlightenment to the Nigerian and did a holistic and thorough analysis of relevant provisions of the constitution as they relate to elections, Promotion of public interest and consciousness in participatory elections, organize series of campaigns to educate the citizens on their civic rights and electoral duties.

James (2016) carried out a study on the Influence of Mass Media on Voting Pattern in Rural Areas of Nigeria. Mass information, in a democracy, is a necessity. As a result, the roles of mass media as harbingers of information, education and providers of entertainment become indispensable. However, the mass media of mass communication have failed in their effort to provide the traditional social

responsibility functions with which they have been identified for ages, especially in the rural areas of Nigeria. The rural dwellers in Nigeria are not adequately informed about the political process and development like their urban counterparts. Many newsworthy events, which should be reported by the media, are not given attention in the rural areas. Radio, which is the favorite and the most loved among the rural dwellers, has not also done enough to orientate, re-orientate, educate, enlighten, and mobilize the rural areas. This is because most programmes done on radio are elitist and are carved in a foreign Language-English-which most rural dwellers do not find easy to comprehend. Programmes about agriculture which concern the rural dwellers, if done at all, are aired in English Language. The study is driven by agenda-setting theory and two step- flow of information theory. The agenda setting theory posits that the media think for the audience by disseminating information which they think is important. The two step-flow of information theory states that some individual have better access to the media than others in the society. These people are called opinion leaders, while the others who have less access to the media of communication are called opinion-followers. The study recommends the establishment of community radio station in rural areas for political mobilization and information.

Bappayo, Abubakar and Kirfi (2021) carried out a study on The Impact of Mass Media on Political Mobilization Process in Plateau State Radio Television Corporation, Jos (PRTVC), Nigeria. The objective of the study was to determine the level interference of government in the activities of mass media affects the political mobilization process. The population consists of all the staff of Plateau Radio Television Corporation Jos (PRTVC) who answered the simple designed choice and opened questionnaires. The sample size of 196 employees of Plateau Radio Television Corporation Jos was used to gather relevant information for analysis. The researcher used frequency and percentage as a statistical tool of analysis to analyze all data collected. The study established that without a vibrant press and free flow of information, government cannot fully function to its full potentials. It also revealed that freedom of the press is vital to the growth of Nigerians democracy. The research thus recommends that in order to ensure, efficient and unbiased political mobilization by the mass media, there should be total autonomy, which will in turn ensure a free and independent press.

Maxwell M. N (2016) carried out a study on newspaper readers' perception of campaigns for eradication of corruption in Nigeria, which result of the finding indicates that Nigerian Citizens exposure to newspaper reports on corruption has a significant impact on their attitudes and behaviors regarding corruption. This fact does not need to be over-emphasized. It agrees with the agenda-setting theory of the media. But the only regret here is that over 70 percent of Nigerians still live in the rural areas where most of the newspapers do not reach. Hence, there is the dire need to encourage the setting up of community newspapers in our country. Media owners should also consider the inculcation of oramedia channels in their publication plans. Oramedia are the indigenous means of communication by the people amongst themselves, done through both human and non-human vehicles like town criers, talking drums, the folk songs, drama, festivals (Ugboaja, 1985; Osho, 2011). Wilson (1999), defined oramedia or traditional media in Nigeria as the local means of communication by the rural people which essentially sustain the information needs of this segment of the population. There is nothing wrong in making town criers in our villages, newspaper vendors or distributors. Apart from creating jobs for them, it will help the newspapers to reach even seemingly inaccessible remote areas of the country, and thus, disseminate the messages of anti-corruption there. When this is done, the rural people will no longer support those traditional rulers who are in the habit of giving chieftaincy titles to people of questionable characters and means. According to Ayodele (2013), a critical element of a country's anti-corruption program is an effective media. When journalism exposes flaws and even corruption within the various bodies of the state (the courts, police and anti-corruption task forces), corruption is put on check. If the resulting public pressure leads to a reform of those bodies, the long-term effectiveness and potential of the media to act as a counterweight against corruption is strengthened. But Ayodele (2013) quotes Sowumi et al. (2012) as asserting that the persistence of Transparency International (2002) in setting Nigeria among the bottom five nations in its annual Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) since 1995 is an indication that the media has not performed this role effectively. Meanwhile, the dilution of the efforts of the Nigerian media in the fight against

corruption according to Ayodele (2013), hinges on a plethora of reasons, such as lack of freedom of media professionals to access, verify and publish accurate information, and independence of media houses and their ability to access independent sources of financing. Competition, outreach and credibility of media are other important factors affecting media performance (Nogara, 2009). Each of these is examined by Ayodele (2013) accordingly as follows: • Freedom of expression – Media freedom of expression is essential to investigate and report incidences

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on two theories framing theory and social responsibility theory. Framing theory was first posited by an anthropologist Gregory Bateson, 1972, and Erving Goffman was credited with coining the term in 1974 in his book *Frame Analysis* but in (Arowolo, 2017) sees it as a mass communication theory that refers to packages and present information to the public. It is a social science theory that examined how people perceive reality and how media shape those perceptions. The major premise of framing theory is that an issue can be viewed from variety of perspectives and be construed as having implications for multiple values or considerations.

Framing theory examines in this study how women politician is often portrayed differently in the newspaper than their male counterparts, with frames emphasizing their gender, family roles or emotional responses. It equally the non-coverage or slight coverage stories on women in politics that leads to negative perception about their competence and suitability for leadership. The framing theory suggests that the media can play a significant role in shaping peoples' perception of women in politics by being aware of these biases in newspaper houses and challenge the to promote more equitable representation of women in politics in their news stories.

Social Responsibility Theory: This theory can be said to have been initiated in the United States by the Commission of the Freedom of Press, 1947 (Eze, 2011, pp.83-85). This assertion was supported by Folarin (2002, p.31) when he posited that the theory owes its origin to Hutchinson Commission on Freedom of the Press, set up in the United States of America in 1947 to re-examine the concept of press freedom as emancipated in the Libertarian or free theory.

However, according to Okoro and Agbo (2003, p.23), the major opinion being canvassed by the social responsibility theorists certainly agreed that the media should fulfill certain obligations and expectations for the society. They went further to say that it is in doing so that the media become socially responsible. Social responsibility theory emphasized that mass media/the press shall have a limited freedom to report issues of public interests. This theory advocates the use of newspapers to inform Nigerians about women in politics especially in Enugu state.

Research Methodology

The survey method was chosen as the most suitable approach, involving the use of a questionnaire to collect data from Enugu state residents. Wimmer and Dominick (2016) assert that survey allows researchers to examine lifestyle information motives, intentions and so on. This method was adopted using questionnaire to evoke answers, and views from Enugu state residents on newspaper coverage of women in politics. Creswell (2012) describes survey research designs as procedures in quantitative research design in which investigators administer a survey to sample or to the entire population of people to describe the attitudes, opinions, behaviors, or characteristics of the population. The entire population of Enugu State residents is considered the population of the study. Enugu State is located in Nigeria and consists of 17 Local Government Areas. The study focused on the residents of Enugu State due to its relevance to the research objectives. A projected population estimate of 4,411,100, a sample size of 384 was drawn using the Australian sample size calculator with confidence level of 95% and confidence interval of 5.0%. The random sampling method was equally utilized. : The researcher administered 384 questionnaire and 378 were returned, representing 97.4% of the total copies of the questionnaire shared, 6 questionnaire were not properly filled while 4 were not returned, showing mortality rate of 2.6%, given the total of 100%

Data Presentation and Analysis

According to Nwodu (2006, p. 172), data analysis is an explanation of factorial information generated in the course of a study. Data can be analyzed to further overall goal of understanding social phenomena achieved through the process of description, explanation and production (Ikeagwu, 1998). The researcher analyzed the data thus;

Table 1: Perception of Enugu state newspaper readers on newspaper coverage of stories on women in politics

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
To a large extent	315	84.2%
Moderately	36	9.6%
To some extent	14	3.7%
Do not know	9	2.4%
Total	374	100%

Source: Field survey, 2024

From the above analysis of data in the table 1, indicate that out of the 374 respondents, 315 or 84.2% of them agree that *to a large extent*, the newspapers that circulate in Enugu state do not give coverage to stories on women in politics; 36 or 9.6% of the respondents claimed that they have *moderately* noticed that stories on women in politics are not given coverage by newspapers. While 14 representing 3.7% of them claimed that they *to some extent* perceived that women in politics are not covered by newspapers, the other 9 or 2.4% of the respondents were *indifferent*

Table 2: Analysis of research questions based on level of prominence and depth newspapers give to stories related to women in politics

Depth	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Above 7 inches	4	1.1
6-7 inches	11	2.9
Below 6 inches	359	96
Total	374	100%

Source: Field survey, 2024

From the above analysis of data in the table, out of 374 news items published by newspapers on women in Nigerian politics, 4 (1.1%) of them measured above 7 inches, 11 (2.9%) of them measured 6-7 inches and 359 (96%) of them measured below 6 inches. It means that there are not much prominence and in - depth stories on women in politics in the newspapers.

Conclusion

Newspapers carry out their social responsibility of informing their readers of the things happening in their environment and beyond, on their daily publication. It also helps them to provide a complete package of enticing stories (with other reports). Some readers make their choice of newspaper based on what interest them and the reports they understand and enjoy. The findings revealed that women mostly feature in stories about domestic violence, accidents, and natural disasters than stories about their professional abilities and expertise most especially political affairs. Respondents in Enugu state perceived newspapers coverage of women in politics as inadequate.

Recommendations

From the findings the researcher recommended that the print media most especially the newspapers should report stories that pertains to women in politics given it an in depth coverage to encourage more women to become interested in politics. Then, future researchers should investigate how the social media report women in politics as the traditional media are not reporting it adequately.

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